

Supporting Information

1. Supplementary Figures

6 **Supplementary Fig. 1.** The preliminary step for identification of the active substance from cell-
7 free supernatant (CFS) of *L. acidophilus* 4356. a) Tricine SDS-PAGE profile of concentrated
8 CFS at different concentration, (i) Protein marker, (ii) Samples based on their concentrations,
9 respectively, are shown from left to right (i- iii). This is well illustrated by the low performance
10 of this peptide. The peptides have shown in figure with arrows. b) Partial separation of the
11 protein bands with relatively high concentration in CFS by ammonium sulfate precipitation at
12 different concentrations of 50% (Fraction I) and 80% (Fraction II). MRS
13 broth without inoculated probiotic as negative control. c) Anti-pyocyanin activity of the fractions
14 I & II. i) Qualitative and, ii) Quantitative comparison ($\mu\text{g/ml}$).

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17 **Supplementary Fig. 2.** HPLC of crude protein (left). After ammonium sulfate precipitation,
 18 crude protein run in water-acetonitrile with 0.1% TFA as mobile phase, in a gradient from 5 to
 19 95% acetonitrile at a flow rate of 1 ml/min with an ODS-3 C18 column. Tricine SDS-PAGE of
 20 semi-purified peptide (right). The initial analysis of the purity of the chromatogram peak-related
 21 fraction was performed by the SDS-PAGE. The desired peptide band is shown in blue box.

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۲۴ **Supplementary Fig. 3.** The DNA sequencing of the gene encoding ACD. Multiple alignments
 ۲۵ of the Acidocin 4356 gene with the sequencing results of the ACD coding region (by two
 ۲۶ primers F and R) have been shown. The overlapping gene coding for ACD with the sequencing
 ۲۷ short read fragments generated from forward, reverse, and both primers have been shown in
 ۲۸ orange, blue, and green, respectively. The sequence corresponding to the leader peptide has
 ۲۹ indicated by a red box.

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32 **Supplementary Fig. 4.** MIC₅₀ and MVIC₅₀ determination method. a) Monitoring of bacterial
33 growth by FDA fluorescence method, and b) The experimental data were obtained by evaluating
34 the production of virulence factors. The linear regression analysis was used to determine these
35 parameters. MIC₅₀ and MVIC₅₀ were defined as the concentrations at which bacterial cell
36 viability and the average of virulence factors production reached to 50%. The MIC₅₀ and
37 MVIC₅₀ values were calculated as 79.43 µg.ml⁻¹ (a), and 13.90 µg.ml⁻¹ (b), respectively. Error
38 bars represented the standard error (SD), referring to the three repetitions of the measurement.

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ε) **Supplementary Fig. 5.** The reaction of ACD peptide with CFC from *P. aeruginosa*. CFC
εϰ treatment was performed with different concentrations of ACD. The PCN level was measured at
εϳ wavelength 695 nm. Treatment with ACD did not change the level of PCN in CFC.

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εϛ **Supplementary Fig. 6.** Examination of hemolytic activity of ACD. The percentage of hemolysis
εϜ coincided with an increase in peptide concentrations up to $>3\times\text{MIC}$ by measuring RBC cells
ε⊗ lysis at a wavelength of 540 nm. The experiment was performed in two different runs with three
εϩ replications.

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 02 **Supplementary Fig. 7.** The analysis of Live/Dead bacterial cells using flow cytometry
 03 technique. In order to study live and dead bacterial population, the bacterial solution was isolated
 04 by centrifugation at $4000 \times g$ for 10 min, and stored in 0.1% NaCl solution for living cells and
 05 70% isopropyl alcohol for induction of bacterial death. The live and dead bacterial cells were
 06 incubated at room temperature for one hour. After one hour, the cells were isolated and stored in
 07 buffer, and viability measurements were done using flow cytometry. The percentage of live and
 08 dead cells in bacterial populations (control group), based on the ratio of the fluorescence signal
 09 intensity of the FDA and PI to the total stained cells, was 97.11 and 99.7, respectively. In order
 10 to gating selection, unstained and single-stained bacterial cells were used with FDA or PI. Cell
 11 suspensions were labeled with FDA (green dots) and (red dots) PI and FDA-PI (orang dots).

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64 **Supplementary Fig. 8.** Evaluation of five QUARK models of ACD using DOPE score. Model
 65 3, as a reliable model of ACD, was employed for the simulation.

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 79 **Supplementary Fig. 9.** The pulmonary pathology indicators for classification of different
 80 groups. Numbers have been reported by pathologist based on the n=3 mice in two independent
 81 experiments.

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83 2. Supplementary Excel File

84 **Supplementary Excel File 1.** Proteome Discoverer (PD) read-out files of peptide
 85 identification by LC-MS/MS (a, b, c). Three independent gel extraction and peptide
 86 identification were performed.

87 3. Supplementary Video

88 **Supplementary Video 1.** The killing of biofilms after treatment with ACD. Cells at
 89 different depths of Pseudomonas biofilms formed after 72 hours without treatment
 90 (right), and after 1 hour of treatment with MIC level of ACD (left side) (Scale bar=50
 91 μm).